

laboratory insects respond differently from field-reared insects, at least in flight performance. Second, the tropical field

population contained a proportion of adults capable of sustaining flights of long duration. Questions to be answered

include whether, how often, and under what conditions the BPH exploits this capability. ■

Soil and crop management

“Catch” crops for summer annual fallow

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Eight crops were evaluated to determine the most suitable as a local summer annual (catch) crop after winter rice. The experiment was in a replicated randomized block design and was continued for 3 seasons (1976-78). The test crops included sesame (locally called gingelly) — the traditional catch crop in the area — as well as short-duration tapioca, groundnut, cowpea, sweet potato, mung bean, finger millet, and black gram. During early growth the crops depended on residual soil moisture and, later, on occasional summer showers.

Performance of crops in summer rice fallow. Kayamkulam, Kerala, India, 1976-78.

Crop	Duration (days)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Returns ^b (US \$/ha)
Tapioca ^c	103 ^d	13.5	487
Groundnut	103	2.8	842
Cowpea	67	0.6	206
Sweet potato	103 ^d	2.8	132
Mung bean	66	0.2	61
Finger millet	103	0.5	123
Sesame	76	0.3	119
Black gram	78	1.3	394

^aMean for 3 seasons. ^bIn terms of the prevailing Kerala market rate. ^cGrown in only 1 season. ^dHarvested before full maturity.

Groundnut gave the highest returns (see table). Although it matures 20 to 25 days later than sesame, it can easily fit into the region's current cropping pattern. The 110-day interval between the winter and autumn rice crops is sufficient for a crop of 103 days duration. Tapioca and sweet potato require more than 110 days to mature.

The growth durations of black gram

and cowpea are similar to that of sesame; their input costs are low and their returns relatively high. Hence for the

local summer rice fallow, groundnut, black gram, and cowpea can be used as summer annual catch crops. ■

Improved management-practices for raising boro seedlings

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Cold temperature in the boro season (min, 10-12°C) retards and stunts the growth of seedlings, especially of modern rices, even if transplanting is delayed to

60 days after sowing. BRRI experiments indicate that improved seedbed management involving the use of farm-yard manure and night cover during the cold season can produce more vigorous seedlings. When transplanted at 30 or 45 days after sowing, such seedlings were taller, had higher dry matter production, and lower mortality. They produced higher yields in a shorter growth period than conventionally grown seedlings. ■

Root distribution and root biomass production of rice under different soil water regimes in Entisols of northern India

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Rice plants were grown in the greenhouse under four water management regimes: a) saturation (0-0.1 atm) throughout crop growth, b) saturation up to maximum tillering and flooding up to ripening, C) flooding up to maximum tillering and saturation up to ripening, and d) con-

tinuous flooding (water depth of 3 ± 5 cm) throughout crop growth. Plants were spaced 40 cm apart to keep their roots separate.

Horizontal root growth (distance between the plant base and the farthest root cores around the hill) was measured. Cores were taken from various lateral zones around the plant with a 2-cm-diameter core sampler. The roots were spray washed and separated from the cores.

The water management practices at the initial vegetative phase affected root distribution and root mass production

Root distribution and biomass of rice under 4 water regimes in Entisols, Varanasi, India.

Water regime	Root color	Intensity of distribution	Lateral spread (cm)	Vertical spread (cm)	Root biomass production (g/hill)
Continuous saturation	Deep brown	Sparse	13	26	12.2
Saturation + flooding	Brown	Less abundant	14	23	13.2
Flooding + saturation	Light brown	Abundant	16	18	15.6
Continuous flooding	Lighter brown	Dense mat	16	16	18.1